

ISic0445

I.Sicily inscription 0445

Language

Latin

Type

funerary (?)

Material

stone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found in Syracuse in December 1767 (CIL)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. S(it) · t(erra) · t(ibi) · l(evis)

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation (en)

May the earth rest lightly on you

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491673

EDCS 21900507

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus*

Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum. Berlin. At 10.7166 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650769>)

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